

If I were to encapsulate my entire journey within the realm of the Wounds of Wisdom research in just a single word, that word would undoubtedly be "WOW."

About the Training:

Looking back on this incredible journey with the Wounds of Wisdom research project and the youth mental health events we organized, I am filled with a profound sense of gratitude and accomplishment. My journey with Wounds of Wisdom led me on a path of personal growth that I never anticipated. Starting from the training which for me, was not just academic exercises; each online and on-site meeting that I attended, proved to be a treasure of great insights and learnings that not only helped me develop a deeper understanding of the society we live in but also set me on a journey of self-awareness. These experiences aided me in validating my emotions and navigating through challenging feelings, while also teaching me the significance of practicing self-care.

The primary takeaway, for which I am immensely grateful to the WOW research, is that it helped me cultivate greater empathy and provided me with skills I never knew I needed.

Adding to that, a concept that has long puzzled me revolved around the question of why should I engage in conversations with individuals facing challenging circumstances if I lack the means to directly improve their situations. This feeling often led me to avoid engaging in uncomfortable dialogues with disadvantaged individuals around me. I had concerns that such interactions might unintentionally come across as condescending or dismissive, inadvertently diminishing the value of their vulnerability and

potentially causing further harm to someone who is already hurting, but as I delved into the narratives of others, I found myself shedding preconceived notions and judgments, replaced by a genuine desire to listen, learn, and truly understand humans around us. Through WoW, I realized that sometimes, aiding someone through their struggle is all about offering a genuine ear and a secure space for them to openly share their feelings and that sometimes just allowing someone to speak their heart out without being judgmental can provide immeasurable support, enabling them to express themselves in a manner that fosters a sense of importance and, most importantly, empowerment which unknowingly might just be all that they need to walk through this difficult phase. In a world where people only listen to speak, I learned the skill to listen to understand and connect with individuals with whom I may not be sharing common problems but what I do share is the society that we live in and the sky that covers us.

Community Awareness Events

During this period, I also had the privilege of contributing to two youth mental health events. The impact of these youth-centered events, with themes like "Dreams to Realities" and "I Am My Superhero," was nothing short of transformative, both for the audience and me. These topics resonated deeply with me, encapsulating the aspirations I have held for a long time and the sense of responsibility I have always felt toward empowering the youth and making a positive change in their lives. The event served as a manifestation of my dream to contribute and give back to the community.

This opportunity to engage with young minds, share insights, and create safe discussion spaces was humbling and inspiring.

As the sessions unfolded, I could see the spark of empowerment igniting within the young participants. The discussions, stories, and interactive sessions appeared to bring about a noticeable shift in the perspectives of young people.

One of the most touching takeaways was the realization that despite facing underprivileged circumstances, the youth we engaged with were brimming with dreams and resilience. This revelation shattered stereotypes and highlighted the potential that resides within them, which shows the importance of providing platforms where these dreams can be nurtured and transformed into tangible realities.

The expressions on the faces of young people and the sparkle in their eyes after we concluded our events were enough to make all the months of effort, brainstorming sessions, and meticulous planning seem entirely worthwhile!

In closing, I would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to Professor Panos and Dr. Sajda for providing us with this invaluable opportunity and for their unwavering support and guidance throughout this journey. Their patience and acceptance of all our ideas and opinions have been truly remarkable. Last but

not least, I want to express my gratitude to my fellow peer educators. As I pen these words, a rush of dopamine floods over me, reminiscing about the moments spent with them. Our light-hearted banter on the bustling streets of Karachi, as we made our way back home, served as the perfect conclusion to the insightful workshops. The seats we occupied transformed into spaces where

laughter, discussions, and shared experiences flourished. Through these conversations, we forged a bond that extended beyond the project. This group, affectionately known as the "WOW Group," and the camaraderie we shared will forever remain a cherished chapter in my journey.

With gratitude,

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